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EDUCATION KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

O7 TECHNICAL ANALYSIS REPORT (WORK PACKAGE 4)

Project Information

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1. Executive summary

This report builds on previous work from WP2 and WP3, resulting from technical work coordinated by CESGA, with the contributions of Beeznest, Netex and Lusoinfo, and interaction with the rest of the partners, resulting in a reference technical report that describes the Infrastructure definition and guidelines for EKT platform.

Previous O5 report provided a comprehensive list of user profiles aligned with their expectations / needs perceived by final users through academic partners findings, in relation with the platform, aligned with the possibilities of the technology.

O6 report provided the educational and technological framework for development of professional competences in-school placement.

This report, O7, will serve as guidelines to work in the Work Package 4, where all dependencies from previous WPs, current tools, functionalities, and goals are set.

2. Diagram

EKT INFRASTRUCTURE SCHEMA

3. Technical solutions to meet user requirements

The following table serves to match the perceived needs from prospective user roles with a technological solution within EKT platform.

Requirement 1:	Users communication (text, audio, video)
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short text messages between students and tutors from school / University, both groupal or individual - Possibility to link to documents/files within the message, as well as embedding images/videos - Multiconference possibilities, both individual and group conferences.
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	Use Talk component in NextCloud platform. It will also provide a useful link between shared documents and one to one / group text communication and videoconferencing for EKT users.
Integration capabilities and standards	Talk component is a plugin accessible from EKT dashboard.
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	<p><i>Talk access from EKT dashboard</i></p> <p>Direct URL access: https://nc.ektproject.eu/apps/spreed/</p>

Talk videoconference integration

Talk text-chat integration

Requirement 2:	Collaborative work
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share documents between students/tutors/Uni professors - Co-create shared documents among several students - Publish created docs in students e-portfolio - Teachers create (interactive/not) training materials for students - Students create (interactive/not) training materials for school / eportfolio
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	<p>Nextcloud for sharing files will allow to create / Share (with different users inside or outside platform) / co-create</p> <p>Netex content cloud: different suppliers can be used, content production can be monitored.</p> <p>E-portfolio as a newly created tool within the training section (Chamilo).</p>
Integration capabilities and standards	<p>Integration from Dashboard (Nextcloud)</p> <p>Integration from Chamilo (Content Cloud and e-portfolio)</p>
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	<p>The screenshot shows a user interface for a portfolio in Chamilo. At the top, it says 'Cesga DEMO course / Portfolio'. Below that are icons for adding content, folders, and users. The main section is titled 'Portfolio' and includes a 'Select a learner portfolio' dropdown with a search box. There are also tags for 'Chamilo', 'elearning', 'work', 'drawing', 'action research', 'Observation', and 'Activity 1'. A search bar and a 'Filter' button are at the bottom left. On the right, a post titled 'Mi first contribution to portfolio' by María José Rodríguez is shown, with a creation date of 3 months ago. Below the post, it says 'This is my latest work' and '3 comments · Add a new comment'. Three comments are listed: 'Elena Revyakina' (about 1 month ago, 'Lovely!'), 'Eduardo Cardoso' (3 months ago, 'Test Eduardo'), and 'Mjoao Vaz' (3 months ago, 'Mui bonito!').</p> <p><i>Chamilo E-portfolio functionality development</i></p>

The image shows two screenshots of Nextcloud Collaboration. The top screenshot displays a file manager interface with a sidebar on the left containing navigation options like 'Recent', 'Favorites', 'Shares', and 'Tags'. The main area shows a list of files and folders, including 'Demo document.docx', 'Readme.md', 'Talk', 'Expense report.odt', and several 'Coordination' folders. The bottom screenshot shows a content editor interface with a page title 'Page Title 3', a section title 'Block Title', and a text block containing placeholder text. A right-hand sidebar offers various content insertion options like text, images, and tables.

Nextcloud Collaboration

ContentCloud

Requirement 3:	Tools to improve evaluation/reflection
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-portfolio understood as a “learning diary” where students publish their progress, with texts, documents, images, etc. - Videoconferences & webinars for tutoring, evaluation, etc.
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	<p>Video Evaluation&Conferences: Talk component</p> <p>E-portfolio: Chamilo development and integration</p>
Integration capabilities and standards	E-portfolio developed with xAPI compliance to send the data to the LRS

Comments (+
links, images,
etc)

Cesga DEMO course / Portfolio

Portfolio

Select a learner portfolio
Search users

See my portfolio in this course

Tags

- Chamilo
- elearning
- work
- drawing
- action research
- Observation
- Activity 1

Search

Filter

Mi first contribution to portfolio

María José Rodríguez · Creation date: 3 months ago

This is my latest work

3 comments · Add a new comment

- Elena Revyakina · about 1 month ago
Lovely!
- Eduardo Cardoso · 3 months ago
Test Eduardo
- Mjoao Vaz · 3 months ago
Mui bonito!

Chamilo E-portfolio

Talk videoconference integration

Requirement 4:	Administration tools: (groups, contents for groups, individualized learning paths, etc.)
Examples of Use	User management (students, tutors, professors, universities, etc.) creating users, deleting, assigning users to schools, etc. Assignments to individual or groups to learning paths / portfolios, folders...
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	EKT platform centrally manages users through CAS and single sign on. Users are created by the top roles (administrator and coordinators), and then, assigned to universities/schools. HEI tutors can assign them to certain folders, learning paths, etc.
Integration capabilities and standards	CAS, SSO, EKT APP Management Interface, EKT APP communication with integrated apps through API and custom interfaces.

Comments (+ links, images, etc)

The screenshot shows the 'My university general data' section with the following statistics:

- Number of students: 5
- Number of groups: 2
- Number of admins: 1
- Number of coordinators: 2
- Number of tutors: 1

The 'Overview of assigned schools' section shows:

- Number of schools: 3
- Number of school tutors: 1

Navigation links include 'View students', 'View groups', 'View administrators', 'View coordinators', 'View tutors', 'View schools', and 'View school tutors'.

Management interface

The 'Manage university' section includes the following navigation links:

- List of students
- List of groups
- List of admins
- List of coordinators
- List of tutors

Below these links is a search bar and a table with the following data:

Name	Surname	Actions
Ahmad	Skywalker - UT	[Icons for edit, delete, etc.]

Additional navigation links include 'List of schools' and 'List of school tutors'.

Detail of management interface – Manage university tutors

Detail of students assignment to tutor – Same process as for courses, groups, universities, schools, etc.

<p>Requirement 5:</p>	<p>Content development tools (exchange docs, repository...)</p>
<p>Examples of Use</p>	<p>Creation of documents to share with students Sharing and collaborative editing of docs</p>
<p>Suggested tool/s feature/s to address it?</p>	<p>For online courses, users can select SCORM and LTI packages so we can benefit from having a strong learning analytics platform. In EKT dashboard, training section includes a Cloud Content Creation platform which is already LTI and xAPI compliant, and integrated with Chamilo, which provides the training platform . EKT Content cloud allows a lot of collaborative options to create content between different profiles, plus providing a lots of integrations and creation possibilities.</p>
<p>Integration capabilities and standards</p>	<p>Scorm, LTI</p>
<p>Comments (+ links, images, etc)</p>	<p><i>ContentCloud creation tool</i></p>

Requirement 6:	Tracking of the process: (learning analytics tools): Unified environment (stress)
Examples of Use	Teacher needs to know who the students were attending to a videoconference.
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	Chamilo as the VLE, Learning Locker as the LRS and all the content has to be created with xAPI format, by using Netex's platform. E-portfolio and communication will be xAPI compliant to allow productive analytic possibilities.
Integration capabilities and standards	xAPI traces log to xAPI traces
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	<p><i>Example of xAPI trace stored into LRS</i></p>

Requirement 7:	Ethical concerns: (data protection, GRDP, intellectual property issues, etc.)
Examples of Use	When an user is added to the system, data processing consent must be stored.
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	Academic partners send consent to students. This consent is stored by the university.
Integration capabilities and standards	Capability to enable or disable users on demand.
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	To be developed

Requirement 8:	Compatibility and interoperability (single sign-on, etc.)
Examples of Use	User doesn't have to log in several times to use different tools. User rights and affiliation to institution/ groups are consistent between tools
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	We provide SSO in the platform. This SSO feature allows us to be authenticated into the different tools we're going to use like content cloud, Chamilo, Nextcloud etc etc.
Integration capabilities and standards	CAS-SSO Central Database. User data exchange between platform API's
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	<p style="text-align: center;">https://app.ektproject.eu</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Centralized SSO entry point for the EKT platform</i></p>

Requirement 9:	Services and Tools connected (APIs)
Examples of Use	Possibility of using standard files and formats within the EKT platform
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	A Document edition with collaborative capabilities linked to the platform: OnlyOffice 100% which is an open solution similar to Office 365.
Integration capabilities and standards	Open XML format OpenDocument format

- Comments (+ links, images, etc)

Onlyoffice integration

Requirement 10:	Technical and pedagogical support during the pilots
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support to partners to use tools integrated in EKT platform ▪ Support to partners / tutors to apply EKT methodology
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technical partners are providing support on tools developed and integrated in EKT platform before the pilots, and will be providing it during pilots: screencasts, FAQs, email, or through videoconference. ▪ Lusoinfo is providing videotutorials to integrate in EKT platform.
Integration capabilities and standards	
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	Under development

Requirement 11:	Personalized interfaces according to each role
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Each user should see the tools / resources adequate to his/her needs in EKT pilots
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 5 profiles have been defined: HEI/School coordinator, HEI/School professor/tutor, student, besides a common platform administrator role (global and per country). ▪ A strong integration of tools allows the persistence of user rights and access across all features and tools of EKT platform. ▪ All tools in EKT platform match the rights defined for each profile and have been discussed with partners to accommodate the necessities.
Integration capabilities and	

standards

Comments (+
links, images, etc)

Contact info from my university

University assigned tutor info

Anakin Skywalker - UT
@SKYWALKER@CESGA.ES
12345

University coord info

Name	Email	Telephone
Kencobi - UC Obi-One	DEMO_COORDINATOR@CESGA.ES	1234
coord Test	test_coord@cesga.es	234234

My groups

Groups

Name	Description	Actions
Padaawan's group	BLABLABLA	i

Courses

Course	Description	Content
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Student view - Management section

My university general data

Number of students: 5
Number of groups: 2
Number of coordinators: 2
Number of tutors: 1

Overview of assigned schools

Number of schools: 3
Number of school coordinators: 1
Number of school tutors: 1

Manage university

List of students

Show 10 entries

Picture	Name	Surname	Actions
	Sito	Dyas	i d x
	Plo	Koon-STUD	i d x

HEI coordinator view – Management Section

Demo user accounts per role:

Username	Password	Role
DEMO_ADMIN@CESGA.ES	DEMO_ADMIN2021	COUNTRY/UNIVERSITY ADMINISTRATOR
DEMO_COORDINATOR@CESGA.ES	DEMO_COORDINATOR2021	UNIVERSITY COORDINATOR
DEMO_TEACHER@CESGA.ES	DEMO_TEACHER2021	UNIVERSITY TEACHER
DEMO_SCOORDINATOR@CESGA.ES	DEMO_SCOORDINATOR2021	SCHOOL COORDINATOR
DEMO_STEACHER@CESGA.ES	DEMO_STEACHER2021	SCHOOL TEACHER
DEMO_STUDENT@CESGA.ES	DEMO_STUDENT2021	STUDENT
DEMO_STUDENT2@CESGA.ES	DEMO_STUDENT2021	STUDENT
DEMO_STUDENT3@CESGA.ES	DEMO_STUDENT2021	STUDENT

Requirement 12: Safety protocol -Data protection (IP)	Safety protocol - Data protection (IP)
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establish protection against unwanted access to EKT platform ▪ Backup data recovery
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	EKT platform uses SSL and many privacy and protection features. Other security measures are firewall, VM protection, and daily backups as part of the normal procedures in CESGA's cloud platform.
Integration capabilities and standards	
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	

Requirement 13:	Universal design (accessibility)
Examples of Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Offer easy access to all major Operative Systems ▪ Offer adapted access for mobile devices (phones and tablets) through app ▪ Offer a simple environment according to accessibility standards, to facilitate access for all types of users. ▪ Multilanguage
Tool/Feature developed/selected to match this need	The platform should comply with the recommended usability guidelines. However, given the foreseen complexity of elements, it would be difficult to achieve WAI AAA standard
Integration capabilities and standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bootstrap ▪ Grid ▪ Flexbox ▪ L10n translation standard ▪ Other similars
Comments (+ links, images, etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Platform translated to English, Spanish, Portuguese and German ▪ Language automatically selected based in browser language. ▪ Content Fits automatically to the with/height of the device

Project Partners
